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Public health in an unstable world

Resilience of the population of the Hellenic Republic as a weapon of defense

Introduction

In an era marked by geopolitical tensions and threats from multiple fronts, the resilience of the Hellenic Republic's population stands as a formidable defense mechanism. With the resurgence of Russian aggression, the intensifying conflict between Beijing-China and Taipei-China, and the perennial threat from Turkey, Greece's strategic preparedness is crucial. Historically, Greece has demonstrated extraordinary resilience, overcoming centuries of Turkish occupation while preserving its cultural and religious identity. This enduring spirit underscores the nation's capacity to withstand and adapt to contemporary challenges, reinforcing its sovereignty and stability.

Civil Protection

Civil protection in the Hellenic Republic is a multifaceted system designed to safeguard the population, property, and cultural heritage against a wide range of hazards, including natural disasters, technological accidents, and armed conflicts. This framework is coordinated by various governmental and non-governmental organizations, ensuring an integrated and effective response to emergencies.

Legal framework

The legal basis for civil protection in Greece is established through national laws and regulations, which outline the responsibilities of different agencies and the mechanisms for coordination. These laws mandate the establishment of civil protection plans at national, regional, and local levels, ensuring a cohesive approach to disaster management.

Effective warning systems are crucial for civil protection. Greece employs a combination of modern technologies and traditional methods to alert the population about imminent threats. This includes mobile apps, social media, sirens, and broadcast media, ensuring timely and widespread dissemination of warnings.

Preparedness involves training, public education, and drills to ensure readiness for emergencies. The Hellenic Fire Service, along with other agencies, conducts regular exercises to test and improve response capabilities. In the event of a war or a major disaster, a coordinated response is activated, involving multiple agencies and resources.

Health protection in uncertain times

In crisis situations, health services must be capable of handling large numbers of casualties. The National Health Operations Center coordinates the medical response, ensuring that hospitals and emergency services can provide adequate care. Additionally, specialized medical task forces are prepared to be deployed in severe emergencies.

The Hellenic Republic has an excellent first aid system, Mobile Medical Units (MMU) and Mobile Emergency Medical Units of First Aid Ambulance are ambulances staffed by highly trained medical personnel for emergency pre-hospital Medicine and trained ambulance crews equipped with specialized equipment and medicine for advanced support and stabilization of the vital functions of the patient. In times of crisis or war every single of these highly equipped ambulance units can function a first aid station, reducing the work load of the hospitals. These units are always ready and can be rapidly deployed to disaster sites, providing critical care and stabilizing patients before they are transported to hospitals.

Recognizing the psychological impact of disasters, Greece integrates psychosocial support into its health protection framework. Trained mental health professionals are deployed alongside medical responders to provide immediate psychological first aid and ongoing support to affected individuals, helping to mitigate the long-term effects of

trauma. In times of crisis psychological resilience is no luxury but an important asset.

Robust public health surveillance systems are essential for early detection and management of disease outbreaks, which can occur in the aftermath of disasters. The Hellenic Center for Disease Control and Prevention (*Κέντρο Ελέγχου και Πρόληψης Νοσημάτων*) which became the National Public Health Organization (NPHO) (*Εθνικός Οργανισμός Δημόσιας Υγείας, ΕΟΔΥ*) monitors public health data to identify potential outbreaks and coordinate responses, ensuring that appropriate measures are taken to protect the population's health.

Despite well organized public protection citizens should be prepared for any kind of disaster. Every citizen suffering from a chronic condition should ensure they have a three-month supply of their essential medications at home. This precaution is vital for maintaining health and continuity of care during emergencies, such as natural disasters or geopolitical conflicts that might disrupt supply chains. By having a sufficient reserve of medications, individuals can manage their conditions effectively without interruption, thereby reducing the risk of exacerbations and complications during periods when accessing pharmacies or medical facilities may be challenging. This proactive measure is a critical component of personal and public health resilience.

Collaboration with International Health Organizations

Greece collaborates with international health organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the relevant institutions of the European Union. This collaboration enhances the country's ability to respond to health emergencies by sharing knowledge, resources, and best practices. Protection of all kinds of cultural heritage is an often a very underestimated aspect of psychological stability. Therefore Greece places significant emphasis on the protection of its cultural heritage. Measures include the documentation, and safeguarding of cultural assets. In collaboration with international

bodies, Greece has developed protocols to protect cultural heritage during conflicts and disasters.

Volunteers

Volunteers play a crucial role in civil protection. Many institutions support and train volunteer organizations and integrates them into the emergency response framework as a shadow civil army. This collaboration improves the overall ability to respond to and recover from disasters. Many citizens have knowledge or skills that help to keep daily life as stable as possible.

Conclusion

Civil protection in the Hellenic Republic is a robust and dynamic system that integrates legal, technical, and community-based approaches to manage and mitigate the impacts of disasters. Continuous improvement through training, technology, and international cooperation ensures that Greece remains resilient in the face of both natural and man-made hazards.

All references at

<https://civilprotection.gov.gr>